

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Social sustainability at farm level may also change due to new practices aimed to increase soil biodiversity

In most projects introducing new practices to increase farm sustainability, the environmental and economic consequences are thoroughly studied. The social consequences, however, often remain unseen. This is unfortunate, since factors such as labour requirement or farmer well-being may affect the adoption of practices as much as environmental or economic factors. Therefore, in SoildiverAgro a rapid social sustainability assessment tool (SSAT) was developed and applied to the case studies.

The SSAT was developed in three steps:

- 1. The social themes that could be influenced by changes in soil management were identified by all project partners, inspired by existing SATs. This yielded both in internal (relating to farmer and family) and external (relating to societal expectations) themes.
- 2. In a farmer survey in Finland, Estonia, Belgium (Flanders) and Spain (Galicia and Murcia) was asked: "Suppose you

would start using [soil practice surveyed] on your whole farm, which of these social issues do you feel might also change?". The importance indicated was used as weights for the themes in the SSAT (table 1).

- 3. Indicators to measure the social themes were either taken from existing SATs or developed based on questionnaires used in social research in agriculture.

The SSAT was tested in 9 case studies in 5 regions, asking farmers about social sustainability in case of business-as-usual (BAU) or with the new practice they had applied on their farm.

It was shown that in most cases changing soil management practices not only had an impact on biodiversity, environment and farm economics, but also on social sustainability. In 7 out of 9 cases a change was found, which was positive in 6 cases and negative in 1 case. In these cases changing social sustainability was a factor in whether or not to adopt the practice after the trial was finished.

Social sustainability theme	Weight
Amount of labour	85,6%
Quality of life, including work/life balance	19,8%
Administrative burden	28,0%
Your or your workers health due to changed pesticide use	24,4%
Being proud of being a farmer and of your farm	37,8%
Stress due to changes in farming practices	29,2%
Contacts/networks with whom you can exchange experiences	33,4%
Employment on your farm (non-family temporary or permanent employment)	8,1%
Landscape provision by your farm	36,8%

Figure 1: Farm level social sustainability (%) in 9 SoildiverAgro case studies, comparing business-as-usual (BAU) and a new soil management practice (new). The percentage point difference between BAU and NEW is indicated.

Table 1: Social sustainability themes assessed in SoildiverAgro and the percentage of farmers who valued each theme (= weight given to the theme)

KEYWORDS

Social sustainability, assessment tool, soil management, farm level, farmer

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